

Learning Locally: Participatory Methods for Agent-Based Conservation Models of Carnivores

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Abstract

1. Agent-based models of animal populations require behavioral rules—the conditional mechanisms that govern how animals respond to contexts, competitors, and constraints. Telemetry provides movement patterns useful for validation but cannot reveal the mechanisms that produced them. We developed and applied an 80-question framework for eliciting such rules through structured workshops with conservation practitioners.
2. Applied to tiger conservation in South Asia, the framework systematically varied context across behavioral domains. Practitioners contributed observations unavailable from movement data: how competing physiological needs shape daily decisions, why water availability determines territory size, what triggers corridor use during monsoon. Their input shaped model architecture, not just parameter values. Practitioner knowledge has limitations—it incorporates published literature, and inferences can be wrong—but it complements telemetry: practitioners provide candidate mechanisms to build models; telemetry provides patterns to validate them.
3. Solution/Practical Implication: Conservation modelers developing agent-based models for wildlife populations can use the 80-question framework to systematically elicit behavioral mechanisms from field practitioners. The framework—structured as behavioral domains × focal behaviors × contextual modifiers—ensures comprehensive coverage while generating input that translates directly into model rules. Practitioners should be engaged as critics throughout model development, not just as initial informants.

Keywords: agent-based modeling, participatory methods, local ecological knowledge, conservation, tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*)

1. Introduction

“The wisdom of people who live close to the land should not be ignored; they have survived for generations because they understood the balance.” ~ Jane Goodall

Technological advances such as remote sensing and animal tracking have transformed ecology by providing quantitative data that was previously unattainable (Jeltsch et al., 2025). However, this transformation comes at a cost: the empirical knowledge gained by rangers, hunters, and naturalists who observed their animals for decades may be fading—a pattern now recognized as the "extinction of experience" within ecology itself (Soga & Gaston, 2025).

Fieldwork-based publications have declined 20% since the 1980s while modeling studies rose 600% (Ríos-Saldaña et al., 2018), and institutional pressures actively discourage field-intensive research (Rafiq et al., 2024). Fifty years ago, researchers would observe their animals directly, noting what resources they used and how they behaved (Cagnacci et al., 2010). Nowadays, ecologists spend less time in the field becoming acquainted with their study species, leaving them with only a nascent idea of what animals are actually doing (Hebblewhite & Haydon, 2010). Moreover, the stories told by practitioners about territorial disputes, seasonal movements, and individual quirks are often considered too anecdotal or context-dependent to be useful—particularly for model development. Yet modelling—the very approach increasingly used to understand and manage natural systems—requires exactly what practitioners observe: how animals respond to contexts, competitors, and constraints. Models are needed because controlled experiments with natural systems are usually not feasible. Well-designed and tested models allow us to explore the consequences of different scenarios.

Particularly useful are agent-based models (ABMs; in ecology often also referred to as individual-based models; IBMs), as they allow population-level patterns and dynamics to emerge from the behaviour of individual organisms. Agent-based modelling, and ecological modelling in general, have advanced over recent decades (Stillman et al., 2015; Grimm & Berger, 2016) and are increasingly used for decision support.

However, while ABMs can make good use of tracking data, they cannot run on movement patterns alone. An ABM must specify what, for example, a tiger does when it encounters a rival at a kill, how it responds when prey density drops, whether a mother with cubs flees or hides when she detects a resident male. These conditional rules constitute the model's core. Patterns contain information about system organization, but in coded form—they require decoding (Grimm et al., 2005).

Agent-based models succeed when natural history details are incorporated; they are most productive when based on species for which behavioral parameters are already available or can be collected (Stillman et al., 2015). GPS telemetry records movement outcomes: where an animal went, when it was active, how its range overlapped with others. This information is essential for validation. But multiple mechanisms can produce identical patterns (Grimm et al., 2005; Wiegand et al., 2003). As for tigers, they might avoid an area because of human disturbance, competitor presence, prey scarcity, or past negative experience. The movement is the same; the mechanisms differ entirely. A model might validate against observed patterns while being inaccurate about causation—and therefore inaccurate about how the system will respond to interventions. Hidden Markov models can classify movement states, but inferring behavioral mechanisms from location data remains fundamentally limited (Glennie et al., 2023; Patterson et al., 2008).

Conservation practitioners can provide what telemetry cannot: the mechanisms themselves. A nature guide who has tracked the same tigers for fifteen years knows not just where they go, but why—and how that why differs between individuals, seasons, and contexts. A ranger who has patrolled buffer zones for two decades knows that tigers cross agricultural land during monsoon when streams flood their usual routes, but only at night and only through specific corridors. Wildlife managers rely on such knowledge to flag what monitoring systems miss (Kadykalo et al., 2021; Fazey et al., 2006).

Still, representing this empirical knowledge so that it can be used as the basis for agent-based modelling remains challenging. For modelling tiger populations, management and conservation, we therefore developed an 80-question framework for structured elicitation of behavioral rules from conservation practitioners. We applied this framework in a workshop with 20 practitioners in South Asia's Terai Arc Landscape, a tiger conservation priority area. The framework, workshop process, results, and limitations are reported in the following.

2. Context

2.1 Setting

The Terai Arc Landscape spans lowland forests connecting protected areas through corridors that tigers use for dispersal and territorial establishment. Conservation planning requires understanding how tigers will respond to different interventions—where they will go, whether corridors will function, how populations will persist.

We began developing a tiger ABM and realized that published literature and available telemetry data could not provide the behavioral rules the model needed. Telemetry studies in the region had collared only a handful of tigers—valuable individuals, but a fraction of the population. Territorial negotiations, dominance shifts, and dispersal decisions could not be observed from GPS points alone.

2.2 Participants

The workshop convened 20 conservation practitioners: nature guides leading wildlife tourism, rangers and forest guards patrolling protected areas, conservation officers from government and NGO positions, community patrol members from buffer zone villages, and one retired chief warden with 40 years of experience. These participants had 2–40 years observing the same tiger population. What matters for such work is knowledge acquired through extensive observation of an area or a species (Huntington, 2000). Participants were 40% women. Different professions observe different behaviors at different times: nature guides during tourist hours, rangers at varied hours including night, community members at the human-wildlife interface. Local observers are present at all times of day and year-round, covering different circadian rhythms and seasons (Braga-Pereira et al., 2022). This professional diversity meant the same population was observed from multiple vantage points—a form of triangulation.

3. Methodology

3.1 The 80 Questions Framework

The elicitation framework assigned five groups to behavioral domains: sustenance (hunting/eating), mating and resting (mating behavior/resting behavior), movement patterns (day/night), exploration (home range establishment/use), and territory (size/shape). Each group addressed two focal behaviors. Eight modifier questions per behavior systematically varied context: individual differences, sex, age, season, habitat, temperature, precipitation, and temporal change. This structure yielded 80 questions ($5 \text{ groups} \times 2 \text{ behaviors} \times 8 \text{ modifiers}$), ensuring coverage while maintaining comparable format across groups. The systematic modifiers ensured that elicitation targeted decision processes rather than behavioral descriptions (Hoffman et al., 1998). The complete framework is provided in Appendix A.

3.2 Workshop Process

The workshop ran five hours with four 40-minute sessions separated by breaks. Each session covered four questions at 10 minutes each. Groups recorded responses on paper in English and local languages in text and drawings (see figure 1), presenting summaries to the plenary twice during the day. This duration is consistent with evidence that data saturation in qualitative research typically occurs within 9–17 interviews (Hennink et al., 2022; Guest et al., 2006).

Figure 1: Drawings produced in the workshop in response to questions, detailing tiger space use in different seasons and habitat use.

3.3 Facilitation Challenges

Participatory processes depend more on how they are conducted than on which tools are used (Reed, 2008). We encountered predictable challenges: translation between languages; participation inequality from professional hierarchies; varying comfort with drawing versus writing for spatial questions; tendency toward either hyper-specific anecdotes or vague generalizations. Small groups, structured turn-taking, base maps, and time limits helped but did not eliminate these issues. These challenges are inherent to participatory research (Voinov & Bousquet, 2010; Reed et al., 2009).

4. Results

A common assumption is that workshops provide parameters—numbers to plug into a pre-designed model. Practitioners provided more than this. Their input shaped model architecture: not what values to use, but what kind of model to build (Stillman & Goss-Custard, 2010). Specifically, practitioner accounts led to two principles that structure the model's behavioral architecture: spatial memory formation and need-based movement allocation. In the following we describe how practitioners' knowledge shaped the design and validation of our agent-based tiger population model.

4.1 Architectural Contributions

Need-based allocation. Practitioners described tigers balancing competing demands. When asked about mating across seasons, they explained: "*In hot temperature tiger has to move a long area to [find] prey and water so this season is not good for mating.*" The model implements seven needs competing for a daily energy budget: hunger, thirst, mating, safety from competitors, safety from humans, rest, and exploration. Allocation is proportional to urgency—an architecture derived from practitioner accounts.

Spatial memory. Practitioners described tigers navigating learned resource locations: "*Old tiger has idea about water, grassland and resting place. So they can easily collect food.*" The model implements memory sets for water, shade, food, and competitor locations, updated through exploration.

Water as spatial organizer. One nature guide with 25 years of experience provided place-specific knowledge: "*When I started my work there was less presence of water, tigers had to move a lot. By now there is more presence of water, they don't have to move much.*" This 25-year observation identified water availability as the primary factor explaining territory size changes. The model implements faster thirst accumulation than hunger, making water the dominant spatial constraint.

Maternal state. Motherhood changes behavior: "*Female tiger is aware about her cubs. Every time she like security of cubs so she keep them in hide place and she rest in a open and high place.*" The model adds cub-hunger and cub-thirst to the mother's need calculation, and cub-memory-locations to the mother's spatial memory properties.

4.2 Stories as Data

Practitioners communicated knowledge through stories—specific events with specific tigers in specific circumstances. Stories serve as vehicles by which humans understand experience, often encapsulating cause-and-effect relationships (Shivakumar et al., 2025; Dhee et al., 2019). Our framework systematically elicited these narratives. Structured elicitation yields knowledge absent from published sources, including perceptual cues and decision heuristics that practitioners rarely articulate (Hoffman et al., 1998; Drescher et al., 2013).

4.3 Territory Geometry

Early model prototypes represented territories as circular, equal-sized areas. When practitioners reviewed output, they objected: "*This is not how it develops over a hundred years.*" One group labeled their drawing "*NOT GEOMETRIC*," describing territories shaped by landscape features: track lines, river channels, fire lines, foot trails.

This feedback led to an architectural change. The model does not define territories as geometric shapes. Instead, territories emerge from marking behavior, competitor avoidance, and resource distribution. Shape is an outcome, not an input. Practitioners also described nested, sex-specific territories—"3–4 female tiger under the command of 1 male tiger"—matching published findings (Goodrich et al., 2010).

4.4 Validation

Our practitioner-informed tiger model, BaghSim, was tested across four water availability scenarios (model and ODD available at CoMSES.org; see Banerjee et al., submitted for full details on results). Without population-level calibration, five empirical patterns emerged: sexual dimorphism in home range sizes (males 3.3–3.6× larger than females), male-biased dispersal distances (1.4× farther), natal philopatry in females, sex ratios matching empirical observations (0.74–0.85 male-to-female), and age at first reproduction consistent with field data. A sixth pattern—polygynous breeding units with males encompassing 1–5 female territories—emerged without prescribed social rules. Home range sizes fell within empirical ranges: females 33–58 km², males 121–206 km². Territories contracted around scarce water and expanded along rivers through individual settlement decisions, demonstrating that the mechanisms practitioners described produce realistic spatial organization when implemented.

5. Discussion

5.1 Complementary Sources

Practitioner knowledge should not replace but complement telemetry. The two serve different functions:

Camera traps and GPS collars reveal who was where and when—essential for validation. But validation requires a model to validate. Building that model requires behavioral rules, and practitioners observe these mechanisms directly. Scientific monitoring typically provides synchronic data (short time series over large areas); practitioners provide diachronic information (long time series in small areas) (Moller et al., 2004).

Those who live and work in a system may observe phenomena that scientists would not capture (Voinov & Bousquet, 2010). Practitioner knowledge has real limitations. It incorporates published literature; the distinction between direct observation and received knowledge is often blurred (Brook & McLachlan, 2008). Practitioners observe correlations and infer causation—sometimes wrongly. Experts are subject to overconfidence, availability bias, and anchoring (Kuhnert et al., 2010; Burgman et al., 2011). Coverage is biased toward accessible areas and charismatic individuals. Structured elicitation across multiple observers reduces error but does not eliminate it (Martin et al., 2012).

The framework addresses these limitations through design (as shown in figure 2). Professional diversity provides a form of triangulation: nature guides observe during tourist hours, rangers during patrols including night, community members at the human-wildlife interface—the same behaviors reported by multiple professions carry more weight than single-source accounts. The eight systematic modifiers force practitioners beyond anecdote to pattern: asking how hunting differs by season, age, and habitat prevents reliance on memorable exceptions. Plenary presentations exposed contradictions for group resolution. These safeguards reduce but do not eliminate bias—structured elicitation with diverse practitioners yields more reliable input than informal consultation but remains fallible.

Figure 2. Complementary roles of practitioner knowledge and telemetry data in agent-based model development.

Similar complementary dynamics appear elsewhere. Census counts of bowhead whales in Alaska during the 1970s indicated 2,000–3,000 animals. Inuit whalers challenged these counts—they saw whales in places the census did not survey. Collaboration expanded the census to include aerial and acoustic techniques, resulting in a revised estimate of 6,000–8,000 whales (Fazey et al., 2006). Technology should not replace field biology but be combined with learning from animals in the field (Hebblewhite & Haydon, 2010). Yet such integration remains rare in practice: a systematic review of 912 papers found only 6% genuinely combined complexity science methods with participatory approaches (de Jager et al., 2025). The framework presented here addresses this gap.

5.2 Ownership and Uptake

Modeling choices—regarding structure, data handling, and interpretation—are not purely epistemic but are entangled with values, institutional contexts, and ways of understanding the world (Klein et al., 2024). Models built without local input may encode assumptions that conflict with ground-level realities: global climate scenarios assume 90% African urbanization by 2100, while African participants envision strong rural communities (Aguiar et al., 2020). Our practitioners objected when early model prototypes represented territories as circular—“*NOT GEOMETRIC*,” they wrote—revealing that expert assumptions about spatial organization diverged from observed reality. Such corrections only emerge when practitioners are positioned as critics, not just informants.

Models built with practitioner input are models practitioners will use. Local methods provide one of the few channels through which practitioners can scrutinize science; if methods cannot be tested, findings will probably not be acted upon (Moller et al., 2004). Giving stakeholders the opportunity to challenge model assumptions creates ownership that makes results harder to reject (Voinov & Bousquet, 2010; Barreteau et al., 2003). The circular territory critique exemplifies this: practitioners became continuing critics who improved the model.

5.3 Applying the Framework

The 80-question framework applies beyond tigers. The structure—behavioral domains × focal behaviors × systematic modifiers—fits wildlife ABM contexts where behavioral mechanisms must be elicited from practitioners. The eight modifiers (individual, sex, age, season, habitat, temperature, precipitation, temporal change) capture variation relevant across species. Scale choices in ecological modeling affect which patterns can be observed and what mechanisms can be discovered (Banerjee & Ertsen, 2026); the framework's systematic coverage across modifiers helps ensure that scale-dependent phenomena are not overlooked.

Recommendations:

1. **Diversify participants.** Multiple professions observing the same population provide triangulation. Include practitioners with different schedules (day/night), access points (core areas/boundaries), and observation modes (stationary/mobile)—the same behavior reported independently by a nature guide and a ranger carries more weight than either alone.
2. **Structure the elicitation.** Systematic modifiers prevent gaps and ensure comparable responses. Without structure, workshops drift toward memorable anecdotes; with structure, practitioners are pushed to articulate patterns they have observed but never verbalized.
3. **Document limitations.** Honesty about what practitioners cannot know builds credibility. The BaghSim ODD documents specific limitations identified during the workshop process. Distinguish between behaviors practitioners observe directly (hunting, resting) and those they infer (territorial negotiation, dispersal decisions).
4. **Maintain relationships.** One workshop is a start; ongoing engagement improves both model and uptake. When practitioners see their input reflected in model behavior, they become invested critics—our circular territory correction emerged because participants reviewed early outputs.

Telemetry provides patterns to validate models; practitioners provide mechanisms to build them. Both are necessary, and they are not interchangeable. Participatory methods with field practitioners address this gap directly—as ecological modelers understood before telemetry became the dominant paradigm.

As fieldwork declines and researchers spend less time observing their study species directly, the reservoir of mechanistic knowledge shrinks (Soga & Gaston, 2025). Telemetry data accumulate; behavioral understanding does not. Agent-based models built without practitioner input may validate against observed patterns while encoding mismatched mechanisms—and therefore make inaccurate predictions about how systems will respond to interventions.

The framework presented here offers one response. It does not replace telemetry, nor does it claim that practitioner knowledge is infallible. It provides a structured process for capturing what practitioners observe but rarely document: the conditional rules governing how animals respond to contexts, competitors, and constraints. As ecology becomes increasingly computational, such methods ensure that models remain grounded in the biological realities that only extended field observation can reveal.

Author contributions

I.B. conceived the study, designed the framework, facilitated the workshop, developed the model, and wrote the manuscript. R.T. coordinated practitioner recruitment, provided local expertise, co-facilitated the workshop, and translated all the transcripts. M.W.E. reviewed the manuscript and acquired funding as the principal investigator.

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The 80-question elicitation framework is provided in Appendix A. The BaghSim model and ODD protocol are available at Zenodo [10.5281/zenodo.18554416.]. Workshop transcripts contain sensitive location information and are not publicly archived; anonymized summaries are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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Ethics Statement

The workshops and data collection for this study were conducted as part of larger research projects which received formal ethics approval from the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) TU Delft.

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Appendix A: The 80 Questions Framework

The elicitation framework used 5 behavioral domain groups, each addressing 2 focal behaviors, with 8 systematic modifiers applied to each behavior. This yields 80 questions ($5 \times 2 \times 8 = 80$).

Groups and Behavioral Domains

Group	Behavioral Domain	Focal Behavior 1	Focal Behavior 2
1	Sustenance	Hunting	Eating
2	Mating and Resting	Mating behavior	Resting behavior
3	Movement Patterns	Movement (day)	Movement (night)
4	Exploration	Home range establishment	Home range use
5	Territory	Territory size	Territory shape

The 8 Modifiers

For each focal behavior, participants answered how the behavior differs across:

Modifier	Question Format
1. Individual	How does [behavior] differ between individual tigers?
2. Sex	How does [behavior] differ between male and female tigers?
3. Age	How does [behavior] differ between old and young tigers?
4. Season	How does [behavior] differ between different seasons?
5. Habitat	How does [behavior] differ between habitats?
6. Temperature	How does [behavior] differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. Precipitation	How does [behavior] differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. Temporal change	How does [behavior] differ between now and since you started your job?

Complete Question List

Group 1: Sustenance

Focal Behavior A: Hunting

1. How does hunting differ between individual tigers?
2. How does hunting differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does hunting differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does hunting differ between different seasons?
5. How does hunting differ between habitats?
6. How does hunting differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does hunting differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has hunting changed since you started your job?

Focal Behavior B: Eating

1. How does eating differ between individual tigers?
2. How does eating differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does eating differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does eating differ between different seasons?
5. How does eating differ between habitats?
6. How does eating differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does eating differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has eating changed since you started your job?

Group 2: Mating and Resting

Focal Behavior A: Mating behavior

1. How does mating behavior differ between individual tigers?
2. How does mating behavior differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does mating behavior differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does mating behavior differ between different seasons?
5. How does mating behavior differ between habitats?
6. How does mating behavior differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does mating behavior differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has mating behavior changed since you started your job?

Focal Behavior B: Resting behavior

1. How does resting behavior differ between individual tigers?
2. How does resting behavior differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does resting behavior differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does resting behavior differ between different seasons?
5. How does resting behavior differ between habitats?
6. How does resting behavior differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does resting behavior differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has resting behavior changed since you started your job?

Group 3: Movement Patterns

Focal Behavior A: Movement (day)

1. How does daytime movement differ between individual tigers?
2. How does daytime movement differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does daytime movement differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does daytime movement differ between different seasons?
5. How does daytime movement differ between habitats?
6. How does daytime movement differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does daytime movement differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has daytime movement changed since you started your job?

Focal Behavior B: Movement (night)

1. How does nighttime movement differ between individual tigers?
2. How does nighttime movement differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does nighttime movement differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does nighttime movement differ between different seasons?
5. How does nighttime movement differ between habitats?
6. How does nighttime movement differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does nighttime movement differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has nighttime movement changed since you started your job?

Group 4: Exploration

Focal Behavior A: Home range establishment

1. How does home range establishment differ between individual tigers?
2. How does home range establishment differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does home range establishment differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does home range establishment differ between different seasons?
5. How does home range establishment differ between habitats?
6. How does home range establishment differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does home range establishment differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has home range establishment changed since you started your job?

Focal Behavior B: Home range use

1. How does home range use differ between individual tigers?
2. How does home range use differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does home range use differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does home range use differ between different seasons?
5. How does home range use differ between habitats?
6. How does home range use differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does home range use differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has home range use changed since you started your job?

Group 5: Territory

Focal Behavior A: Territory size

1. How does territory size differ between individual tigers?
2. How does territory size differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does territory size differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does territory size differ between different seasons?
5. How does territory size differ between habitats?
6. How does territory size differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does territory size differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has territory size changed since you started your job?

Focal Behavior B: Territory shape

1. How does territory shape differ between individual tigers?
2. How does territory shape differ between male and female tigers?
3. How does territory shape differ between old and young tigers?
4. How does territory shape differ between different seasons?
5. How does territory shape differ between habitats?
6. How does territory shape differ between cold and hot temperatures?
7. How does territory shape differ between wet and dry conditions?
8. How has territory shape changed since you started your job?

The **temporal change modifier** (question 8 in each set) proved particularly valuable. It captures place-specific knowledge about how tiger behavior has changed with landscape management (water provision, grassland management, anti-poaching efforts) over the span of practitioners' careers—information unavailable from any other source.